

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Eighteen

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 18:0 For the choir director. A <i>Psalm</i> of David the servant of the LORD, ¹who spoke to the LORD the words of this song in the day that the LORD delivered him from the hand of all his enemies and from the hand of Saul. And he said,</p>	<p>Psa. 18:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ לְעֶבֶד</p>
<p>Psa. 18:1 "I love You, O LORD, ^amy strength."</p>	<p>יְהוָה לְדָוִד אֲשֶׁר דִּבֶּר </p>
<p>² The LORD is ^amy ¹rock and ^bmy fortress and my ^cdeliverer,</p>	<p>לִיהוָה אֶת־דְּבָרֵי הַשִּׁירָה</p>
<p>My God, my rock, in whom I take refuge;</p>	<p>הַיּוֹאת בְּיוֹם הַצִּיל־יְהוָה</p>
<p>My ^dshield and the ^ehorn of my salvation, my ^fstronghold.</p>	<p>אוֹתוֹ מִכָּף כָּל־אֹיְבָיו וּמִיַּד שָׂאוֹל : ² וַיֹּאמֶר אֶרְחַמֶּנָּה</p>
<p>³ I call upon the LORD, who is ^aworthy to be praised,</p>	<p>יְהוָה תִּזְקֵנִי : ³ יְהוָה סִלְעֵי</p>
<p>And I am ^bsaved from my enemies.</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא</p>
<p>Psa. 18:4 The ^acords of death encompassed me,</p>	<p>יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>
<p>And the ^btorrents of ¹ungodliness ²terrified me.</p>	<p>אֶפְפוּנֵי חֶבְלֵי־מוֹת וְנַחֲלֵי בְלִיעַל יִבְעֶתוּנִי : ⁶ חֶבְלֵי שָׂאוֹל סָבְבוּנִי קִדְמוּנִי מוֹקְשֵׁי מוֹת : ⁷ בְּצָר־לִי </p>
<p>⁵ The ^acords of ¹Sheol surrounded me;</p>	<p>אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וְאֶל־אֱלֹהֵי אֲשִׁיעַ יִשְׁמַע מִהֵיכְלוֹ קוֹלִי וְשׁוֹעַתִּי לְפָנָיו תָּבוֹא בְּאָזְנוֹ : ⁸ וְתִגְעֶשׂ וְתִרְעַשׂ </p>
<p>The snares of death confronted me.</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>
<p>⁶ In my ^adistress I called upon the LORD,</p>	<p>אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וְאֶל־אֱלֹהֵי אֲשִׁיעַ יִשְׁמַע מִהֵיכְלוֹ קוֹלִי וְשׁוֹעַתִּי לְפָנָיו תָּבוֹא בְּאָזְנוֹ : ⁸ וְתִגְעֶשׂ וְתִרְעַשׂ </p>
<p>And cried to my God for help;</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>
<p>He heard my voice ^bout of His temple,</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>
<p>And my ^ccry for help before Him came into His ears.</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>
<p>Psa. 18:7 Then the ^aearth shook and quaked;</p>	<p>וּמִצוֹדֹתַי וּמִכָּל־טִי אֵלַי צוֹדֵי אֶחְסֶה־בּוֹ מִגְּנֵי וּקְרָן־יִשְׁעֵי מִשְׁגָּבֵי : ⁴ מִהֲלֵל אֶקְרָא יְהוָה וּמִן־אֹיְבֵי אֲנִישֵׁעַ : ⁵</p>

And the ^bfoundations of the mountains were trembling
And were shaken, because He was angry.

⁸ Smoke went up ¹out of His nostrils,

And ^afire from His mouth devoured;

Coals were kindled by it.

⁹ He ^abowed the heavens also, and came down

With thick ^bdarkness under His feet.

¹⁰ He rode upon a ^acherub and flew;
And He sped upon the ^bwings of the wind.

¹¹ He made ^adarkness His hiding place, ^bHis ¹canopy around Him,
Darkness of waters, thick clouds of the skies.

¹² From the ^abrightness before Him passed His thick clouds,
Hailstones and ^bcoals of fire.

¹³ The LORD also ^athundered in the heavens,

And the Most High uttered His voice,

Hailstones and coals of fire.

¹⁴ He ^asent out His arrows, and scattered them,

And lightning flashes in abundance, and ¹routed them.

¹⁵ Then the ^achannels of water appeared,

And the foundations of the world were ¹laid bare

At Your ^brebuke, O LORD,

At the blast of the ^abreath of Your nostrils.

וַיִּתְגַּעְעוּ כִּי-תָרַח לָךְ : 9

עָלָה עֲשָׁן אֲבָאָפוֹ וְאֵשׁ-מִפִּי

תֹּאכַל אֲחָלִים בְּעֶרְוֵי מִמְּנוֹ :

וַיִּט שָׁמַיִם וַיִּרְדּוּ וְעָרְפֵל 10

תַּחַת רַגְלָיו : 11 וַיִּרְכַּב עַל-

כְּרוֹב וַיַּעֲרֵךְ וַיֵּדֵא עַל-כַּנְפֵי-

רוּחַ : 12 יִשֶׁת חֲשָׁךְ אֶסְתָּרוֹ

סְבִיבוֹתָיו סִפְתּוֹ חֲשֹׁכֵת-לַיָּמִים

עֵבִי שְׁחָקִים : 13 מִנְּגַה לְגִדְדוֹ

עָבְיוּ עָבְרוּ בְּרֹד וּגְחָלֵי-

אֵשׁ : 14 וַיִּרְעֵם בַּשָּׁמַיִם |

יִהְיֶה וְעֲלִיּוֹן יִתֵּן קֶלֶד בְּרֹד

וּגְחָלֵי-אֵשׁ : 15 וַיִּשְׁלַח חֲצִצְוֹ

וַיִּפְיֵצֵם וּבִרְקִים רַב וַיִּהְיֶם :

16 וַיִּרְאוּ אֶפְיָקֵי לַיָּמִים וַיִּגְלוּ

מוֹסְדוֹת הַתֵּבֵל מִגְעַרְתֶּךָ

יִהְיֶה מִנְּשַׁמַּת רוּחַ אַפְּךָ : 17

יִשְׁלַח מִמְרוֹם יִקְחֵנִי יְמִנֵי

מִמַּיִם רַבִּים : 18 יִצִּילֵנִי

מֵאִיבֵי עֲזוֹ וּמִשְׁנֵאֵי כִּי-אֶמְצֹ

מִמְּנֵי : 19 יִקְדֵּמוּנִי בַיּוֹם-

Psa. 18:16 He sent from on high, He took me;

He drew me out of many waters.

¹⁷ He delivered me from my strong enemy,

And from those who hated me, for they were too mighty for me.

¹⁸ They confronted me in the day of my calamity,

But the LORD was my stay.

¹⁹ He brought me forth also into a broad place;

He rescued me, because He delighted in me.

Psa. 18:20 The LORD has rewarded me according to my righteousness;

According to the cleanness of my hands He has recompensed me.

²¹ For I have kept the ways of the LORD,

And have not wickedly departed from my God.

²² For all His ordinances were before me,

And I did not put away His statutes from me.

²³ I was also blameless with Him, And I kept myself from my iniquity.

²⁴ Therefore the LORD has recompensed me according to my righteousness,

According to the cleanness of my hands in His eyes.

Psa. 18:25 With the kind You show Yourself kind;

With the blameless You show Yourself blameless;

אִי־דִי וַיְהִי־יְהוָה לְמִשְׁעַן לִי :

²⁰ וַיּוֹצֵאֵנִי לְמַרְחָב יַחֲלִצֵנִי

כִּי חָפֵץ בִּי : ²¹ יַגְמִלֵנִי יְהוָה

כְּצַדִּיק כְּכֹר יָדָי יָשִׁיב לִי :

²² כִּי־שָׁמַרְתִּי דְרֹכֵי יְהוָה

וְלֹא־רָשַׁעְתִּי מֵאֲלֹהֵי : ²³ כִּי

כָּל־מִשְׁפָּטָיו לְנַגְדֵי וְחַקֹּתָיו

לֹא־אָסִיר מִנִּי : ²⁴ וְאֵתֵי

תָּמִים עָמַד וְאֶשְׁתַּמֵּר מֵעוֹנֵי :

²⁵ וַיִּשָּׁב־יְהוָה לִי כְצַדִּיק

כְּכֹר יָדָי לְנִגְדַי עֵינָיו : ²⁶

עִם־חֲסִיד תִּתְחַסֵּד עִם־גֹּבֵר

תָּמִים תִּתַּמָּם : ²⁷ עִם־נָבֵר

תִּתְבָּרַר וְעִם־עֲקֹשׁ תִּתְפַּתֵּל :

²⁸ כִּי־אָתָּה עִם־עֲנִי תוֹשִׁיעַ

וְעֵינָיִם רָמֹזת תִּשְׁפִּיל : ²⁹

כִּי־אָתָּה תִּאִיר נְרִי יְהוָה

אֲלֹהֵי יְגִית חֲשָׁכִי : ³⁰ כִּי־בָךְ

אָרַץ גְּדוּד וּבְאֵלֹהֵי אֲדֹלָג־

שׁוּר : ³¹ תֵּאֵל־תָּמִים דְּרֹכֹו

אִמְרַת־יְהוָה צְרוּפָה מִגֵּן

²⁶ With the pure You show Yourself pure,

And with the crooked You show Yourself astute.

²⁷ For You save an afflicted people,
But haughty eyes You abase.

²⁸ For You light my lamp;
The LORD my God illumines my darkness.

²⁹ For by You I can run upon a troop;
And by my God I can leap over a wall.

Psa. 18:30 As for God, His way is blameless;

The word of the LORD is tried;
He is a shield to all who take refuge in Him.

³¹ For who is God, but the LORD?
And who is a rock, except our God,

³² The God who girds me with strength

And makes my way blameless?

³³ He makes my feet like hinds' feet,
And sets me upon my high places.

³⁴ He trains my hands for battle,
So that my arms can bend a bow of bronze.

³⁵ You have also given me the shield of Your salvation,

And Your right hand upholds me;
And Your gentleness makes me

great.

³⁶ You enlarge my steps under me,
And my feet have not slipped.

Psa. 18:37 I pursued my enemies and overtook them,

And I did not turn back until they were consumed.

הוּא לְכֹל וְהַחֲסִים בּוֹ : ³²

כִּי מִי אֵלֹהִים מִבְּלַעַד־יְהוָה :

וּמִי צָוָר זִוְלָתִי אֶל־הֵינוּ : ³³

הָאֵל הַמְאֲזִינֵנִי חֵיל וַיִּתֶּן

תְּמִים דְּרָכָי : ³⁴ מְשִׁנָּה רַגְלִי

כְּאֵילֹת וְעַל בְּמַתִּי

יַעֲמִידֵנִי : ³⁵ מִלְּמַד יְדֵי

לְמַלְחָמָה וַנְּחַתֶּה קִשְׁת־

נְחוֹשֶׁת זְרוּעֹתַי : ³⁶ וַתִּתֶּן לִי

מִגֶּן יִשְׁעֶךָ וַיְמִינֶךָ תְּסַעֲדֵנִי

וְעֲנוֹתֶךָ תִּרְבֵּנִי : ³⁷ תִּרְתִּיב

צַעֲדֵי תַחְתִּי וְלֹא מָעָדוּ

קַרְסְלִי : ³⁸ אֶרְדּוּךָ אֹיְבֵי

וְאֲשִׁיגִם וְלֹא־אָשִׁיב עַד־

כָּל־וַתָּם : ³⁹ אֶמְחִצֵּם וְלֹא־

יִכְלוּ קוּם יִפְלוּ תַחַת רַגְלִי :

⁴⁰ וַהֲאֲזִינֵנִי חֵיל לְמַלְחָמָה

תִּכְרִיעַ קַמִּי תַחְתִּי : ⁴¹ וְאֹיְבֵי

נִתְּתָה לִי עֶרְךָ וְיִמְשְׁנֵנִי

אֲצַמִּיתָם : ⁴² יִשְׁוּעוּ וְאִין־

מוֹשִׁיעַ עַל־יְהוָה וְלֹא עָנָם :

³⁸ I shattered them, so that they were not able to rise;

They fell under my feet.

³⁹ For You have girded me with strength for battle;

You have subdued under me those who rose up against me.

⁴⁰ You have also made my enemies turn their backs to me,

And I destroyed those who hated me.

⁴¹ They cried for help, but there was none to save,

Even to the LORD, but He did not answer them.

⁴² Then I beat them fine as the ^adust before the wind;

I emptied them out as the mire of the streets.

Psa. 18:43 You have delivered me from the contentions of the people;

You have placed me as head of the nations;

A people whom I have not known serve me.

⁴⁴ As soon as they hear, they obey me;

Foreigners submit to me.

⁴⁵ Foreigners fade away,

And come trembling out of their ¹fortresses.

Psa. 18:46 The LORD lives, and blessed be my rock;

And exalted be the God of my salvation,

⁴⁷ The God who executes vengeance for me,

And subdues peoples under me.

⁴⁸ He delivers me from my enemies;

43 וְאַשְׁחָקֶם כְּעָפָר עַל-פְּנֵי-

רוּחַ כְּטִיט חוֹצוֹת אֲרִיקָם :

44 תִּפְלֹטְנִי מִרִיבֵי עַם

תִּשְׁיַמְנֵי לְרֹאשׁ גּוֹיִם עִם לֹא-

יִדְעֵתִי יַעֲבֹדוּנִי : ⁴⁵ לְשִׁמְעַ

אֲזֵן יִשְׁמְעוּ לִי בְנֵי-יִכָּר

יִכְחָשׁוּ-לִי : ⁴⁶ בְנֵי-יִכָּר

יִבְלֹוּ וַיִּתְרַגְּוּ מִמַּסְגְּרוֹתֵיהֶם :

47 תִּי-יִתְּוָה וּבְרוּךְ צוּרִי

וַיְרוֹם אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׁעֵי : ⁴⁸ הָאֵל

תַּנּוֹתֵן נִקְמֹת לִי וַיִּדְבֹּר

עַמִּים תַּחֲתָי : ⁴⁹ מִפְּלֹטֵי

מְאִיבֵי אֶרֶץ מִן-קָמִי

תִּרְוַמְנֵי מֵאִישׁ חָמָס

תִּצִּילֵנִי : ⁵⁰ עַל-כֵּן אֹדוּךָ

בַּגּוֹיִם אִיהוָה וּלְשִׁמְךָ

אֲזַמְּרָה : ⁵¹ מִגִּדְל [מִגִּדְלִל]

יִשׁוּעוֹת מְלָכִים וַעֲשֵׂה חֶסֶד |

לְמַשִּׁיחוֹ לְדָוִד וּלְזֶרְעוֹ עַד-

עוֹלָם :

Surely You lift me above those
who rise up against me;
You rescue me from the violent
man.

⁴⁹ Therefore I will give thanks to You
among the nations, O LORD,
And I will sing praises to Your
name.

⁵⁰ He gives great deliverance to His
king,
And shows lovingkindness to His
anointed,
To David and his descendants
forever.

Targum

Psa. 18:1 For praise. About the miracles that occurred to the servant of the LORD, David, who sang in prophecy in the presence of the LORD the words of this song about all the days that the LORD delivered him from the hand of all his enemies and from the sword of Saul. ² And he said: I will love you, O LORD, my strength. ³ O LORD, my strength and my security and the one who delivers me; the God who has chosen me has brought me near to fear him; my shield, from whose presence is given me strength and redemption over my enemies; my security. ⁴ David said in praise: "I pray in the LORD's presence, and from my enemies he redeems me." ⁵ Distress has surrounded me, like a woman who sits on the birthstool and has no strength to give birth and so is in danger of death; a band of abusive men has terrified me. ⁶ Armies of sinners have surrounded me; those armed with deadly weapons have confronted me. ⁷ When I am in distress, I pray in the presence of the LORD; and in the presence of my God I make supplication; and he accepts my prayer from his temple, and my petition in his presence is received by his ears, and is granted. ⁸ The earth trembled and shook and the foundations of the mountains tottered, and split, for he was angry with it. ⁹ The arrogance of Pharaoh went up like smoke; then he sent his anger like a burning fire that consumes before him; his rebuke burns at his utterance like coals of fire. ¹⁰ And he bent down the heavens, and his glory was manifested, a dark cloud a path before him. ¹¹ So he was manifested in his strength over swift cherubim; and he proceeded in might on the wings of the storm-wind. ¹² And he made his presence dwell in the mist, and surrounded himself with the clouds of his glory as a covering; and he made favorable rains to fall on his people, and mighty waters from the massed clouds of darkness on the wicked from the eternal heights. ¹³ From the splendor of his glory the clouds of heaven passed by in rebuke like the coals of fire and burning hail from his word. ¹⁴ And the LORD gave a shout from heaven, and the Most High raised up his utterance; he cast hail and coals of fire. ¹⁵ And he sent his word like arrows, and scattered them; [he sent] many lightning bolts, and confounded them. ¹⁶ And the depths of the sea became visible, and the pillars of the world were uncovered at the rebuke of the LORD, from the utterance of your mighty wrath. ¹⁷ He sent his prophets, [he who is] a mighty king who reigns in strength; he took me [and] delivered me from many Gentiles. ¹⁸ He delivered me from my enemies, for they are strong; from my foes, for they prevailed against me. ¹⁹ They confronted me in the day of my wandering; but the word of the LORD was my support. ²⁰ And he brought me out to a broad place, he delivered me because he was pleased with me. ²¹ The LORD will requite me according to my merit; according to the cleanness of my hands he will answer me. ²² For I have kept the proper ways in the LORD's presence; and I have not walked in evil before the LORD. ²³ For all his judgments are revealed in my sight, to do them; and his covenants I will not remove from me.

²⁴ And I was blameless in fear of him; and I kept my soul from sins. ²⁵ And the LORD rewarded me according to my merit; according to the cleanness of my hands in the presence of his word. ²⁶ With Abraham, who was found pious in your presence, you showed much mercy; with his seed, Isaac, who was complete in fear of you, you completed your favorable word. ²⁷ With Jacob, who was pure in your presence, you chose his sons from all the Gentiles, and separated his seed from all that is unfit; but with Pharaoh and his seed, and the Egyptians who thought evil thoughts against your people, you confounded them in their thoughts. ²⁸ Because you are going to redeem the people, the house of Israel, who are esteemed among the peoples in exile; and by your word you will abase the mighty nations who prevail over them. ²⁹ For you will light the lamp of Israel that was extinguished in the exile, for you are the lord of the light of Israel. The LORD my God will bring me out of darkness into light; he will show me his eternal consolation which is to come to the righteous. ³⁰ For by your word I will pass through armies; and by the word of my God I will subdue mighty citadels. ³¹ God [is he] whose ways are true; the Torah of the LORD is pure; he is a shield to all who trust in him. ³² For because of the miracle and deliverance that you will perform for your Anointed, and for the remnants of your people who will remain, all the Gentiles, nations, and tongues will confess and say, There is no God but the LORD, for there is none besides you; and your people will say, There is none mighty except our God. ³³ God, who girds on me a belt in strength, and makes blameless my way. ³⁴ Who makes my feet like hinds'; and he will sustain me in my stronghold. ³⁵ Who teaches my hands to do battle, and who makes my arms as strong as a bronze bow. ³⁶ And you have given me strength and redemption; and your right hand will help me; and by your word you have multiplied me. ³⁷ You have broadened my steps in my place, and my knee has not buckled. ³⁸ I will pursue my enemies; [now] have I destroyed them, and I did not return until I finished them off. ³⁹ I will destroy them, and they are unable to rise; and the slain have fallen under the soles of my feet. ⁴⁰ And you have girded me with strength as a belt to do battle; you have defeated beneath me the Gentiles who rise up to do me harm. ⁴¹ And my foes you have broken in my presence; you have made them turn tail; [thus] my enemies I will destroy. ⁴² They seek help, but they have no redeemer; they pray in the presence of the LORD, but he does not accept their prayer. ⁴³ I have crushed them like clods of earth before the storm-wind; and like the mud of the streets I have trodden them. ⁴⁴ You will deliver me from the discords of the Gentiles; you will keep me by my destiny a benefactor at the head of the Gentiles; a people that I did not know shall worship me. ⁴⁵ At the hearing of the ear, they will obey me; the sons of the peoples will desert in my presence. ⁴⁶ The sons of the peoples will perish, and will go into exile from their palaces. ⁴⁷ The LORD lives, and blessed is the mighty one; for from his presence strength and redemption are given to me; and exalted is God, the strength of my redemption. ⁴⁸ It is God who works retribution for me, and defeats beneath me the Gentiles who arise to do me harm. ⁴⁹ He delivers me from my foes; indeed against those who arise to do me harm you will

make me prevail; you will deliver me from Gog and the armies of rapacious Gentiles with him.
⁵⁰ Because of this, I will give praise in your presence among the Gentiles, O LORD; and I will sing praises to your name. ⁵¹ He works abundant redemption with his king, and shows favor to his Anointed, to David and his seed forever.

Spiritual Analysis

Due to the length of this psalm, it will not be presented in the same way the shorter Psalms are. In addition, a complete rewrite will not be available.

Superscript

This is a song שִׁירָה (shir) of David. He sang about the manifestations of the LORD's sovereignty, which he experienced during his lifetime. David sang to the Sefirot Netzach נִצְחָה (natzacha) who granted him victory over his enemies. David identifies the enemies as the agents of King Saul.

Verse 1

David uses the word אֶרְחַמְךָ (er'cham'cha), which is a love that a child feels for its mother. The Hebrew word is derived from the root word "womb." This also implies that David understood that he was a child of the LORD.

Verse 2

David recalls three distinct manifestations of the LORD's love that he experienced.

1. סֶלְעִי וּמְצוּדָתִי וּמִפְלֹטִי (sal'eer vum'tzudati vum'fal'ti) – "rock and my fortress and my deliverer." David experience the LORD's protection and salvation.
2. אֵלֵי צוּרִי אֶחָסֶה-בּוֹ (aelee tzuri eachaesae bo) – "in whom I take refuge."
David experienced the LORD endowing and shaping him.

3. מִגִּבְרֵי יְקָרְךָ יְשֻׁעֵי מִשְׁנֵבִי (mageenee v'kaeraen-yeesheeeeer meesaegabe) – “my shield and stronghold.” David acknowledged that it is the LORD that led him during his lifetime.

Verse 3

David was versed in the history of the Israelites. He knew that the LORD has always stood by his people. Therefore, he was assured that the LORD would stand with him.

Verse 4

חֲבֵלֵי מוֹת (chaev'lay-mavaet) "Cords of death." This poetic phrase means that death is like a cord that ultimately binds and ropes people. It can also mean the physical pains of life that surround a person. The torrents of ungodliness can be translated as "floods of wickedness terrified me." Thus it can be said that the translation of "cord of death" could be "pains of life." The pains would be the many enemies that David had throughout his lifetime. Imagine the pain David felt when his first-born son Absalom led a revolt against him.

Verse 5

This verse refers to the physical pain that David had endured. In this case, it is a physical pain that leads to death. It is at this time that David calls upon the LORD for renewed life and salvation.

Verse 6

David believed that the LORD heard his voice because he obeyed the Torah laws. Interestingly, David's soul at the time of this writing thought that he wholly followed the Torah. He did not at times. However, the Torah also says that forgiveness for sins is a part of the LORD's law. When David was challenged by the prophet Nathan about the sin with Bathsheba, David immediately repented of the sin and was punished by the child who was born from the incident died. Therefore, David believed he followed the Torah.

Verse 7

David is not describing a part of his life at this point. He mentions earthquakes because ancient people believed that these naturally occurring events resulted from the LORD showing his wrath and anger with His people.

Verse 8

The wrath of the LORD continues from verse seven. Since the cause of the commotion caused by the earthquake was not visible, the people believed that the LORD was showing His anger. It was the conduct of people that drove the LORD to reveal Himself in this manner.

Verse 9 & 10

The people believed that the LORD did intervene in earthly events. However, they could not see the LORD. The Cherub was the vehicle that the LORD used

to visit the Earth to bring judgment. Therefore, it was the Sefirot Gevurah who rode on the Cherub.

Verse 11 & 12

The wrath of the LORD came about with such force that humankind was stunned. The thick clouds of the sky can block the sun's rays, thus making the day dark. Ancient people believed that they could not see the LORD on Earth because He had a hiding place. The LORD was with the Earth but was not going to reveal himself to the people at that time.

Verse 13

The love and majesty of the LORD's sovereignty would bring a new, rejuvenating future, which manifested itself in these catastrophic events.

Verse 14

It appears that the LORD shot arrows upon the Earth in a random fashion. Actually, the arrows were sent forth from the LORD with a definite goal in mind.

Verse 15

The LORD was responsible for the events described in this verse. The power of the breath of the LORD is a reminder of what happened at the Red Sea (Exodus). The power of flooding from the sea is the same power that separated the waters to allow Israel to pass safely.

Verse 16

Even in the time of disaster David still called upon the LORD.

Verse 17

This is a parallelism of the preceding verse.

Verse 18

The calamity may have been brought by the LORD to have profound significance.

Verse 19

וַיֹּצִיאֵנִי לְמִדְבָּר (vayotzeeanee Izmaer'chav) – "he brought me forth also into a broad place." David thanked the LORD for removing those obstacles that confined him during his life journey.

Verse 20

David expressed his loyalty to the LORD. It did not matter what calamity befell David; he never lost his love and commitment to the ways of the LORD.

Verse 21

David kept his attention upon the pathway laid out by the LORD. He tried to do what was right in the eyes of the LORD.

Verse 22

David said that he lived by the definition that the LORD established for social relationships. It could be argued that David was not 100% following the principles. How could David say that he followed the laws about social relationships after the Bathsheba incident? Therefore, it is possible that David penned this psalm before he was king. The superscript says that the psalm was written while Saul was pursuing David. Therefore, the Bathsheba incident had not occurred yet.

Verse 23

David believed that he was keeping himself from sin only because he clung to the LORD. He felt that the LORD was close to him because he mastered his inequity.

Verse 24

David felt the rewards of righteousness. The LORD did not allow Saul's men to find David and kill him. The cleanness of his hands was the sinless David.

Verse 25 & 26

There are three degrees of character.

1. The positive expression of complete, selfless devotion to the service of the LORD and the welfare of His world.
2. The complete subordination of the entire personality to the rule of Divine Law.
3. A person who is still in the process of perfecting him/herself.

The LORD reveals Himself to each person in accordance with their character.

Verse 27

David recognized how the LORD appears to humankind. Saving the afflicted people is one way.

Verse 28

The psalm returns to being focused on David. He wants the LORD to illuminate his path, so he does not walk into darkness. The darkness represents sin.

Verse 29

David acknowledges that his courage comes from the LORD.

Verse 30

The LORD reveals Himself to His people through his acts. The LORD remains constant for a reason, for His acts are always the same. It is the diversity of

human conduct that the LORD's discipline seems to be different. However, the Sefirot Gevurah always judges in the same manner.

Verse 31

Only the LORD can stop the suffering that had been brought down from Heaven. The acts of the Sefirot Gevurah can be halted by the Sefirot Chesed.

Verse 32

David acknowledges that the LORD gave him the strength to combat his enemies with victory. This is the same force that guided his life to moral perfection.

Verse 33 & 34

It is the LORD who trained David to win the war against his enemies.

Verse 35

Now that David had been trained for battle by the LORD, He gave David the shield of salvation. The LORD entrusted David with the task of bringing to Israel the protection and salvation that was promised to the people.

Verse 36

The LORD called David into a position in public life dedicated to the common welfare of the people. Through the LORD's aid to David, he had the strength to do the job without stumbling or swaying.

Verses 37-39

David acknowledged that because of the LORD's help, he was able to destroy his enemies. David believed that his enemies would have intentionally ruined Israel. He probably thought that his enemies would turn Israel away from the LORD and to the pagan gods of the neighboring countries.

Verses 40-42

Not only would the LORD give David victory over his enemies from outside his court, He also gave him victory over the enemies that were lurking in his court. When David defeated an enemy, that enemy would not be able to rise again to challenge him. This would include family members seeking revenge.

Verses 43 & 44

Foreigners who only knew about David by reputation were willing to submit to his commands. David recognized that some of his enemies would conceal their hatred so that they could reap the rewards of being a false friend.

Verse 45

A time would come when David would not have to go to war. Peace existed in Israel, and security was obtained.

Verse 46

David acknowledged that even after the wars are complete and an objective of the LORD's has been achieved, the LORD will still continue to bless his life and be with him.

Verse 47 & 48

This is a repetition of an earlier David statement. David knew that the LORD was always with him. Even after David's victory, the LORD would not leave him, and he knew this.

Verse 49

David envisioned a peaceful future with a dedication to the LORD that should never end.

Verse 50

David received loving kindness from the Sefirot Chesed all the days of his life. David also asked that Chesed would be with his descendants.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

